

X-Ray Methods for the Determination of Uranium and Plutonium in Nuclear Fuels

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Manuscript received 3 November 1995, revised 21 January 1997, accepted 14 February 1997

Nuclear fuel is the heart of a reactor. Uranium dioxide is the fuel used for thermal power reactors and use of uranium and plutonium mixed oxide is under active consideration. Advanced fuel materials like carbides, nitrides and metallic fuels are being developed as the future fuels for the fast reactors^{1,2}. For the reactors to function efficiently and safely, the fuel must meet the stringent specifications laid down by the fuel designer³. Analytical chemistry plays a vital role in determining and furnishing a large part of the data necessary to characterise the materials and the processes used⁴.

Various instrumental methods, like mass spectrometry, spectrophotometry, gamma and X-ray spectrometry are used for the determination of uranium and plutonium in nuclear fuels^{5,6}. The preferred analytical method for the analysis is well-proven Isotope Dilution Mass Spectrometric (IDMS) method. IDMS method involves several steps which include sampling, dilution, spiking, isotope exchange and isotope analysis, requiring skilled workers and several hours of analysis. Measurement methodology must provide timely, rapid, precise and accurate means of determining quantity of special nuclear materials.

X-Ray spectrometric methods play a very important role for the chemical analysis of uranium and plutonium in the nuclear fuels. X-Ray methods are used both in emission as well as absorption modes. X-Ray emission spectrometric methods also known as X-ray fluorescence (XRF) methods have been successfully employed for the analysis of actinide elements. X-Ray emission methods are routinely used for the analysis of nuclear fuel materials in the production plant for the process control and quality assurance of the finished products⁷. In the nuclear fuel reprocessing plant, X-ray emission methods are employed at various stages of the fuel processing for safeguards and nuclear material accounting. X-Ray absorption methods, employing the measurements near the K or L-edge of the element, are used for the determination of elemental concentration. In comparison, X-ray absorption methods are specific, simpler and more suitable for the heavier elements. Absorption edge methods find successful applications in the analysis of uranium and plutonium in the dissolver solution containing large number of fission products with high radiation dose. The role of X-ray emission as well as absorption edge spectrometric methods in the analytical chemistry of nuclear fuels is discussed here.

X-Ray emission methods

The basis of X-ray emission lies in the relationship between wavelength (λ) of the characteristic radiation emitted and the atomic number (Z) of the element,

$$1/\lambda = k(Z-s)^2 \quad (1)$$

where k and s are constants that depend upon the spectral series of the emission line. Characteristic X-ray spectra are excited when a specimen is irradiated with a sufficiently short wave length X-radiation. There are four stages in any scheme of X-ray analysis. These are excitation of the characteristic radiation from the specimen, the selection of a characteristic emission line of the element in question, the detection and measurement of the line intensity and finally correlation of the intensity with the elemental concentration. Before relating the intensity of the fluorescent emission with the concentration of the emitting element, it is usually necessary to correct for the matrix effects. The most practical way to apply a systematic correction is by the addition of an internal standard⁸, if the matrix elements affect the reference line and analytical line in exactly the same way.

XRF methods have the following advantages. (i) A broad dynamic range : elemental concentrations from a few ppm to 100% can be determined. (ii) Samples in solid, liquid or powder form can be used with little or no sample preparation. (iii) Quick and accurate method for the analysis at several stages in nuclear fuel cycle starting from geochemical investigation of ores, processing of ores for actinide elements, manufacturing stages of nuclear fuel cycle, reprocessing of irradiated fuels to nuclear waste disposal. (iv) The assay of elements by X-ray methods is independent of the chemical state; this is an important feature especially in the case of plutonium because this element frequently occurs in several chemical forms and valencies which make normal chemical analysis a difficult proposition. (v) The technique can be easily automated.

Basically, the X-ray spectrometers are of two types⁸ : wave length dispersive (WD) and energy dispersive (ED). The essential difference between the two is in the components used for the separation and detection of the characteristic lines. Main features of the WD and ED systems are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. In the WD systems, the radiation emitted from the sample is collimated and then impinges on an analysing crystal. The crystal diffracts the radiation

Fig. 1. Schematic of wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence technique.

to different extent, according to Bragg's law,

$$n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta \quad (2)$$

where d is the interplanar spacing of the analysing crystal and θ the angle of diffraction. This angular dispersion of the radiation permits the sequential or simultaneous detection of X-rays emitted by elements in the sample. In the ED system, the dispersion is done by solid state detectors. Si(Li) is the most commonly used detector. When a range of X-ray photons falls on the detector an equivalent range of voltage pulses is produced. These output pulses are sorted out according to their heights into different energy bands in a multichannel analyser. All the energies are recorded simultaneously as a spectrum of energy versus intensity. In the WD system, excitation is done by an X-ray tube, whereas the excitation sources in ED system can either be gamma rays from radioactive sources, X-rays from an X-ray tube or characteristic X-rays from a secondary tube.

Fig. 2. Schematic of energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence technique.

Fuel fabrication and reprocessing of the spent fuel are the two important activities of the nuclear fuel cycle where X-ray fluorescence spectrometric methods are routinely

used for the determination of uranium and plutonium. In the fabrication of the nuclear fuel, a number of steps are involved before the fuel is in the final form for loading in the reactor. Chemical quality control requires the determination of various constituents at each stage of fuel fabrication, beginning with the starting material to the finished product³. Dissolver solution from the spent fuel is chemically very complex sample containing about 40 to 50 different elements besides uranium and plutonium exhibiting high radiation dose. The fuel processing is carried out to separate the valuable plutonium and left over uranium in the spent fuel from the highly radioactive fission products which are subsequently immobilised for the safe storage and disposal. Precise quantitative determination of uranium and plutonium is required at various stages of reprocessing for material accounting, process control and for safeguarding of nuclear process solutions.

X-Ray fluorescence spectrometric methods have been used for the analysis of uranium and plutonium employing both L and K X-rays. The energies of some of the prominent L and K X-rays of uranium and plutonium⁸ are given in Table 1. The high energies of the K X-rays of uranium and plutonium require X-ray generators and tubes capable of producing upto 150 keV X-rays. Crystals that provide dispersion in the region of energy of K X-rays are not available and hence ED detector systems are used. The most common choice is one of the L lines, since they provide good intensities in air-path for the solution and solid analysis and can be used with any type of excitation and detection system.

TABLE I—ENERGIES (keV) OF THE PROMINENT L AND K X-RAY LINES OF URANIUM AND PLUTONIUM*

Line	Uranium	Plutonium
L τ_1	20.163	21.401
L β_1	17.218	18.278
L β_2	16.425	17.254
L α_1	13.613	14.279
L α_2	13.438	14.082
K α_2	94.648	99.457
K α_1	98.428	103.653
K β_1	111.289	117.146

*Ref. 8.

Both the WD and ED spectrometers have been used for the determination of uranium and plutonium at various stages of the fuel fabrication, though greater use has been made of the WD system due to lower detection limits and its immunity to the radioactivity associated with the sample. WD detection systems offer better resolution at energy less than 20 keV and more appropriate for the measurement of

L X-rays of uranium and plutonium. (The resolution of WD system typically lies in the range 10–100 keV, compared to a value of 150–200 eV for the ED system⁹). The high resolution of WD spectrometers is an asset in the measurement of the spent nuclear fuels where there is potential for interference from multiple fission products. The actual handling of radioactive material calls for a great many precautions in order to maintain safety standards for radiation hazards. X-Ray spectrometers are suitably adopted for the glove box operations¹⁰ for handling the toxic and radioactive plutonium. Methods have been standardised in our laboratory for the analysis of uranium, plutonium and alloys of uranium and plutonium, using WD spectrometer^{11,12}. Thorium is added as an internal standard. $L_{\alpha 1}$ X-rays of uranium, plutonium and thorium are used for the intensity measurement, using Mo or W X-ray tubes for excitation and LiF (200) crystal for the dispersion. $L_{\alpha 1}$ X-ray energies of uranium and plutonium are well separated (Table 1) and easily resolved by the WD spectrometric system. In the case of high U/Pu ratios as found in the dissolver solution, the major constituent is determined by the internal standard method and plutonium concentration is derived from the U/Pu concentration ratios determined from the intensity ratios of their $L_{\alpha 1}$ lines¹². Typical results of uranium and plutonium determination by X-ray fluorescence in mixed solutions are compared with the chemical results in Table 2. The results show relative standard deviations of less than 0.4% (1σ).

TABLE 2—URANIUM AND PLUTONIUM DETERMINED IN MIXED SOLUTIONS USING THEIR $L_{\alpha 1}$ X-RAY LINES

Pu (mg)			U (mg)		
XRF	Chemical	%dev.	XRF	Chemical	%dev.
6.16	6.15	+0.16	155.74	155.39	+0.23
3.77	3.76	-0.26	84.85	84.89	-0.05
4.19	4.21	-0.48	94.78	94.65	+0.14
4.88	4.89	-0.20	110.29	110.06	+0.21
6.20	6.22	-0.32	140.02	139.90	+0.09
5.40	5.42	-0.37	122.22	122.05	+0.14

Martinelli *et al.*¹³ used ED XRF for the determination of U and/or Pu, both in solution and with pellets, at various stages of nuclear fuel cycle. Matrix effects are minimised by detecting only high energy K-spectrum which are able to pass through the walls of containers.

In the mixed oxides or carbides of uranium and plutonium, the binary ratio method⁸ has been found to be of great use for finding the relative percentage of both the elements. The method is very useful for the quality assurance during the fuel fabrication. The method of binary ratio requires the measurement of the intensity ratios of the two elements for the determination of the relative percentage of uranium and plutonium in the mixed oxide or car-

bide samples. The intensity ratios are correlated with the concentration ratios by the regression analysis to give a calibration equation which can be used to obtain the relative percentage of UO_2 and PuO_2 . The method is quick and eliminates the step of an addition of an internal standard. The method has been applied to powders, microspheres, pellets of mixed oxides and carbides of uranium and plutonium¹², using WD system and $L_{\alpha 1}$ lines for the intensity measurements. The relative percentage of PuO_2 is calculated using the equation,

$$PuO_2(\%) = \frac{C_{Pu}/C_U}{1 + C_{Pu}/C_U} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

An automated ED spectrometer has been used for process control analysis of (Pu,U) O_2 fuel pellets¹⁴ using a 3 kW X-ray tube and a ruthenium foil secondary target to excite pellets. Integrated $L_{\alpha 1}$ lines of uranium and plutonium are measured using dual detectors. The relative standard deviation of better than 0.3% has been reported in a total analysis time of three minutes. ED XRF methods have been used by Tsuji *et al.*¹⁵ for the determination of Pu/(Pu + U) in mixed oxide powder.

X-Ray emission methods become very useful for the determination of uranium and plutonium in spent fuels. The applicability of the technique has been reported^{4,16} to be wide-spread in the reprocessing area, ranging from the dissolver solution to pure product solution which shows that the technique is useful in high radiation field also. On-line or in-line analysis of uranium and plutonium in various process streams has been carried out without interference effects of β , γ activity of fission products^{17,18}. The range of concentration of uranium and plutonium is reported to be 0.05 g dm⁻³ at the lower levels to 500 g dm⁻³ at higher levels with a precision better than 1%.

WD method using W tube has been used for the simultaneous determination of uranium and plutonium in aqueous and organic Purex process solutions of irradiated fuels by measuring intensities of U and Pu $L_{\alpha 1}$ lines^{4,19}. Thorium is used as an internal standard. By adding 10 μ l of the solution on a filter paper, highly active product solution (upto 1000 ci dm⁻³) are studied without interference and without shielding. The method has been used in the analytical range of 1–200 mg of U, Pu/ml with relative standard deviation of $\pm 1\%$. A fully automated WD XRF system has been set up for the analysis of uranium and plutonium in reprocessing solutions²⁰. A glove-box equipped with thin beryllium window permitting primary X-rays to enter the box and fluorescence radiation to return was adopted to the spectrometer. Samples arriving by pneumatic post are transferred to the preparation box. The measurement reproducibility is reported to be better than 0.1% with the absolute errors lying between 0.5 and 0.1%. Matrix

and interference effects are taken care with the use of thorium as internal standard.

The determination of uranium and plutonium in reprocessing solution using ED XRF methods have been carried out using both L as well as K X-rays^{13,21,22}. By using K series lines, robust material, such as stainless steel compatible with a reprocessing plant could be used for the construction of sample cell for on-line measurements.

Absorption edge densitometry

If a monochromatic X-ray beam of intensity I_0 is to be directed through an absorber having mass absorption or attenuation coefficient μ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$), density ρ (g cm^{-3}) and thickness t (cm), the transmitted beam undergoes absorption or attenuation through photoelectric interaction with the matter. The transmitted intensity I is given by

$$I = I_0 (-\mu\rho t) \quad (4)$$

The ratio of the transmitted-to-incident intensity (T) known as transmission, is given as

$$T = III_0 = \exp(-\mu\rho t) \quad (5)$$

The basis of the 'Absorption edge densitometry' is that the mass attenuation coefficient of an element shows discontinuities at the characteristic energies, known as absorption edges. The energies of the so-called absorption edges are characteristics for a given number Z and correspond to electron binding energy in the respective atomic shell (K, L, M. . . etc.) of the given element. The energies corresponding to K and L_{III} absorption edges for uranium and plutonium²³ are given in Table 3. For the K shell photoelectric absorption to take place in uranium and plutonium, the incident radiation must have energy more than

TABLE 3—ENERGIES CORRESPONDING TO K AND L_{III} ABSORPTION EDGES AND THEIR $\Delta\mu$ VALUES*

Absorption edges	Element	Edge energy keV	$\Delta\mu$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$
K	U	115.60	3.65
	Pu	121.76	3.39
L_{III}	U	17.17	54.60
	Pu	18.05	51.90

*Ref. 23.

115.6 keV for uranium and 121.8 keV for plutonium. In the vicinity of an absorption edge, where μ shows a discontinuity, the transmission ratio also exhibits a discontinuity. A photon continuum transmitted through a heavy element bearing sample therefore shows a step-like transmission at K-absorption edge energies of the respective elements. Fig. 3 shows photon transmission as a function of energy for uranium solution. X-Ray continuum after the transmission through a sample containing different elements will show absorption jumps at the energies corresponding

Fig 3 Photon transmission as a function of energy for a uranium solution in nitric acid

to their absorption edge energies which uniquely identify the nature of the element²⁴. The change of μ across a given edge $\Delta\mu$ takes the characteristic values for each element. The $\Delta\mu$ values for uranium and plutonium for K and L_{III} edges²³ are given in Table 3.

The magnitude of the jump in the transmission at the absorption edge is a function of element concentration. For the quantitative analysis, K-edge densitometry requires two transmission measurements, one immediately below and the one immediately above the absorption energy of the element of interest. The fractional density ρ_A of the analyte in a matrix of density ρ_M for a sample of d cm is given by the densitometric equation²³,

$$\rho_A = \frac{\ln[T(E_1)/T(E_u)]}{\Delta\mu_A d} + \frac{\Delta\mu_M \cdot \rho_M}{\Delta\mu_A} \quad (6)$$

where, $\Delta\mu_A = \mu_A(E_u) - \mu_A(E_1)$ (7)

$$\Delta\mu_M = \mu_M(E_1) - \mu_M(E_u) \quad (8)$$

where, E_1 and E_u are the transmission energies below and above the absorption energy of the element concerned, μ_A and μ_M the mass absorption coefficients of the analyte and matrix at the transmission energies. The second part in equation (6) represents the contribution due to matrix composition on the assay results. The matrix effect can even be eliminated if the transmission ratio is evaluated directly at the absorption edge of the analyte, in which case $\Delta\mu_M$ becomes zero for all the elements, other than the analyte. The first term corresponds to absorption edge jump of the mass attenuation coefficient of the analyte. Thus the measurement of the ratio of two transmitted intensities at the absorption edge gives the concentration of the solution.

Absorption edge densitometric methods which are simple, precise and require the measurement of the transmission ratios at the element specific absorption edge have

been found to be very useful and effective for the measurement of uranium and plutonium in high concentrations. Both the L_{III} edge and K edge densitometric methods have been employed. An X-ray L_{III} edge densitometer for the simultaneous non-destructive determination of uranium and plutonium in special nuclear material solution has been used²⁵ for at-line measurements using X-ray generator and Si(Li) detector. For the simultaneous determination of uranium and plutonium concentrations, the measurement difficulties associated with finite detector resolution, proximity of uranium and plutonium L_{III} edges (Table 3) and attenuation of the flux by relatively high uranium concentration affect the analytical results and limit the working range to elemental concentration below 50 g dm^{-3} . In comparison, K-edge methods have been found to be very effective and useful for the measurement of uranium and plutonium concentrations above 20 to 500 g dm^{-3} . For the measurement of transmission ratios at K-absorption edge of uranium and plutonium elements, the photon source may be either a gamma-ray from a radioactive isotope or bremsstrahlung from a X-ray generator. Since K-absorption edges of actinide occur at energies between 110 and 125 keV, the photon source must provide energy higher than values. Se(75) and Co(57) as isotopic sources²⁶ for the measurement of plutonium product concentration and high voltage generators capable of operating at 240 kV for the measurement of uranium concentration in the processed solution²⁷ have been used as photon sources. A high resolution photon detector with associated electronics is used for the intensity measurements. For K-edge densitometry at higher photon energies as required for the analysis of actinide element ($E > 100 \text{ keV}$) high purity small planar Ge detector represents the best choice for the detector.

For K-edge densitometry, it makes no major difference whether a relatively clear solution such as a purified reprocessing product or a chemically complex and highly radioactive sample such as reprocessing input solution of a dissolved spent nuclear fuel is analysed. In both cases, the technique will equally provide an accurate and reliable assay as long as the concentration is more than 20 g dm^{-3} . The high radiation level of the dissolver solution does not affect the results. Though the technique has been widely employed in many laboratories and tested for the dissolver solution, yet it is not suitable for the simultaneous determination of uranium and plutonium in the solution²⁸ with U/Pu ratios higher than 100.

In order to achieve and to maintain the desired level of measurement accuracy and reliability needed for uranium and plutonium accountancy measurement in such input solutions with large dynamic range of concentrations, the techniques of K-edge densitometry and K-XRF spectrometry combined into a single set-up, known as Hybrid K

edge absorptiometry (HKED) has been used for the determination of uranium and plutonium in the reprocess solutions²⁹. Both techniques employ the same X-ray tube as photon source which is operated at 150 kV and 15 mA. Two collimated X-ray beams are directed from the X-ray tube to two separate sample cells. Two separate planar high purity Ge detectors are employed to measure the XRF and absorption edge intensities from the process solution. K-edge method provides the reference basis in terms of an accurately determined uranium concentration while XRF analysis is used for U/Pu ratio. HKED has been installed at the French reprocessing plant and successfully used for the routine determination of uranium and plutonium in the process solutions with accuracy levels of about 0.3% for uranium and 0.6% for plutonium³⁰. Further, the performance evaluation of K-edge densitometer for reprocessing solution over a period of eight years³¹ has shown it to be a reliable method for reprocess solutions. The whole assay process for uranium and plutonium in dissolver solution is thus simply reduced to the measurement of two ratios²⁸: the ratio of X-ray transmissions at K-edge of uranium and the intensity ratio of fluoresced $K_{\alpha 1}$ X-rays from uranium and plutonium.

To summarise, X-ray emission methods are used routinely for the determination of uranium and plutonium at various stages during fuel fabrication. In the mixed oxides and carbides, binary ratio method of intensity measurement of uranium and plutonium has been found to be quick and reliable for the determination of relative percentage of uranium and plutonium. In the field of reprocessing, concentration above 20 g dm^{-3} can be conveniently determined in the dissolver solution by absorption edge densitometric method. For solutions with U/Pu ratio higher than 100, a combination of K-XRF and K-absorption edge densitometry methods into a single technique has emerged as a reliable and accurate method for the determination of uranium and plutonium in the process solutions.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Dr. H. C. Jain, Had, Fuel Chemistry Division and to Dr. V. Venugopal for their interest in this work.

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